

As with Cd^{2+} , the polarograms were recorded with Pb^{2+} solution containing fixed concentration of pyruvate and varying concentration of oxalate, citrate or benzoate at pH 6. All the reduction waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled.

Shaap and McMasters⁷ method was used to calculate the values of A, B, C and β_{ij} ; (Table 2). It is difficult to calculate the predicted values of β_{ij} because we do not have the value of β_{so} or β_{os} for the simple complexes.

The distribution of different complexes formed in each system was calculated. As a representative, the distribution of $Cd(Ox)_i(Pyr)_j$ complexes (α %) as a function of oxalate concentration at $[Pyr]=0.04 M$ is shown in Fig. 2.

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pH-metric Studies of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cadmium-, Magnesium-, Strontium- and Calcium-(II) with Pyruvate and Oxalate or Citrate

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Manuscript received 6 April 1988, accepted 8 July 1988

THE metal complexes of pyruvate are important due to the essential biological role of pyruvic acid, consequently the mixed-ligand complexes containing pyruvic acid acquires a special consideration. In the present paper aims to study the ternary system of the type MAL, where $M=Cd^{2+}, Sr^{2+}, Ca^{2+}$ or Mg^{2+} , A=primary ligand (oxalic or citric); L=secondary ligand (pyruvic).

Experimental

Calvin – Bjerrum’s technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine the protonation constants and the binary and the mixed formation constants of the complexes. pH measurements were carried out on a Orion 601 pH-meter. Oxygen was removed by bubbling pure nitrogen during titrations. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and all the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The titrations were carried out at 30°. Ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at 1.0 M $NaClO_4$.

Results and Discussion

Proton – ligand stability constants : The protonation constants of the ligands (pyruvic HL, oxalic H_2L , citric H_3L) were determined using equation (1),

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \frac{(V_2 - V_1)(N^0 + E^0)}{(V_0 + V_1) T_{L^0}} \quad (1)$$

where, $\bar{n}_A$ is the average number of protons attached per ligand, Y the displaceable hydrogen atoms, E^0 and T_{L^0} are the initial concentrations of the mineral acid and the ligand, respectively, V_1 and V_2 the volumes of alkali of normality N^0 required for the acid and the ligand titrations, respectively, at a given pH value and V_0 is the initial volume of the solution which is 25 ml in each case.

Formation curves are obtained by plotting values of $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH of the system. Values of pK_1^H for pyruvic acid, pK_1^H for oxalic acid and pK_1^H, pK_2^H and pK_3^H for citric acid are estimated by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A=0.5, 1.5$ and 2.5, respectively. The values along with the values reported in literature are given in Table 1.

Metal-ligand stability constant :

Pyruvate – metal complexes : The complex formation between pyruvate and some metal ions, viz. $Cd^{2+}, Mg^{2+}, Sr^{2+}$ and Ca^{2+} is indicated by the shift of metal – ligand titration curve from the ligand titration curve (Fig. 1 for Mg^{2+}). $\bar{n}$ (metal – ligand formation number) is obtained using expression (2),

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V_3 - V_2)(N^0 + E^0) + T_{L^0}(Y - \bar{n}_A)}{(V_0 + V_1) T_{M^0} \bar{n}_A} \quad (2)$$

where, V_2 and V_3 are the volumes of alkali required for the metal complex and the ligand titrations, respectively, at a given pH and T_{M^0} is the total concentration of metal ion (0.01 M). The remaining quantities have the same significance as given in equation (1). The metal – ligand stability constants were obtained from the curve drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL. Values of $pL = -\log [L]$, where $[L]$ is the free ligand concentration, are calculated using equation (3),

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF DIFFERENT LIGANDS

Ligand	Present work			Reported values			Medium	Temp. °C
	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_3^H	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_3^H		
Pyruvate	2.10			2.2 ^a 2.35 ^b	—	—	0.11 M NaClO ₄ 0.5 M KCl	25 25
Oxalate	3.45			3.81 ^c 4.05 ^d 3.31 ^e	1.31 ^c 1.40 ^d 1.08 ^e	—	0.1 M NaClO ₄ 0.05 M NaClO ₄ 2.0 M NaClO ₄	25 25 —
Citrate	5.0	3.70	2.25	5.18 ^f 5.64 ^g 4.88 ^h	4.16 ^f 4.37 ^g 3.83 ^h	2.90 ^f 2.93 ^g 2.40 ^h	2.0 M NaClO ₄ 0.1 M NaClO ₄ 3.0 M NaClO ₄	25 25 25

^aRef. 2, ^bRef. 3, ^cRef. 4, ^dRef. 5, ^eRef. 6, ^fRef. 7, ^gRef. 8, ^hRef. 9.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY OR MIXED COMPLEXES*

Ligand	Cd ^{II}		Mg ^{II}		Sr ^{II}		Ca ^{II}	
	P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R
Pyruvate log K_{ML}^M	2.47	1.95 ^a	2.05	—	2.30	—	2.23	1.08 ^b
Oxalate log K_{MA}^M	2.98	3.22 ^c	2.65	2.39 ^a	2.40	1.25 ^c	—	—
log K_{MAL}^{MA}	3.55	—	3.40	—	2.56	—	—	—
$\Delta \log K$	0.57	—	0.75	—	0.16	—	—	—
$-\Delta G$	4.90	—	4.69	—	3.53	—	—	—
Citrate log K_{ML}^M	3.98	4.20 ^f	3.62	3.40 ^g	2.88	2.70 ^h	3.02	3.40 ^h 3.24 ⁱ
log K_{MAL}^{MA}	3.15	—	2.50	—	2.88	—	2.56	—
$\Delta \log K$	-0.83	—	-1.12	—	0.0	—	-0.46	—
$-\Delta G$	4.35	—	3.45	—	3.97	—	3.53	—

*P = present work; R = reported data: ^aRef. 11, ^bRef. 12, ^cRef. 13, ^dRef. 14, ^eRef. 15, ^fRef. 16, ^gRef. 17, ^hRef. 18, ⁱRef. 19.

$$pL = \log_{10} \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^{j=\bar{n}} \beta_j^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } B} \right)^j / T_L^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0 \right\} \left\{ \frac{V_0}{V_s + V_0} \right\} \quad (3)$$

The formation constants obtained from interpolation at $\bar{n}=0.5$ are listed in Table 2 along with other reported values.

Mixed ligand stability constants: The formation constants of the mixed complexes were evaluated using Irving-Rossotti¹ treatment which extended¹⁰ to ternary systems of the type, $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$. The results in the case of binary systems indicate that $\log K_{M(Ox)}^M$ or $\log K_{M(Cit)}^M$ is greater than $\log K_{M(Pyv)}^M$, so $M(II)$ will be chelated by oxalate or

citrate in preference to pyruvate alone, and it is reasonable to assume that the predominated initial step in the mixed chelate formation must be the coordination of pyruvate by $M(II)$ -oxalate (1:1) or $M(II)$ -citrate (1:1) complex.

The formation curves of the mixed complexes obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL . $\bar{n}$ (average number of pyruvate anion attached to $M(Ox)$ or $M(Cit)$) is calculated using equation (2), where T_M^0 is the concentration of $M(Ox)$ or $M(Cit)$ which equals to the concentration of the metal used and $\bar{n}_s$ is for pyruvate.

The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values were obtained from interpolation at $\bar{n}=0.5$ (Table 2). The $\Delta \log K$ ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{MA}^M$) may be expressed as the equilibrium constant of reaction, $MA + ML = MAL + M$

Fig. 1. pH titration curves: (A) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.99 M NaClO₄, (B) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M pyruvic acid +0.98 M NaClO₄, (C) B+0.01 M Mg²⁺, (D) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M oxalic acid+0.96 M NaClO₄, (E) D+0.01 M Mg²⁺, and (F) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M pyruvic acid+0.01 M oxalic acid+0.95 M NaClO₄.

and its values may be considered as a measure of the coordination tendency of L towards MA relative to M²⁺. The values of $\Delta \log K$ in the present work are positive in the case of oxalate as a primary ligand indicating a stabilisation of the ternary complexes which may be explained on the basis of the cooperative effect between the primary and secondary ligands¹. However, the negative values obtained in the citrate-pyruvate system may indicate a steric effect.

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Syntheses and Characterisations of some Rhenium Complexes with Biguanide and Methyl Biguanide

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Manuscript received 10 February 1988, revised 29 June 1988,
accepted 6 July 1988

COORDINATION complexes of protonated form of biguanides with Re^V were reported by Roy and Ray¹. In this paper we describe the isolation and characterisation of some Re^V complexes with neutral and protonated forms of biguanide and methyl biguanide. The biguanides act as bidentate chelating agent both in the protonated and in neutral forms giving two series of complexes, [ReOX(L)₂] and [ReOX(LH)₂]X₂ and [ReX₄(LH)₂]-X₂, where, X=OH⁻ or Cl⁻, and LH is the protonated form of biguanides. With biguanide itself, two more complexes [Re(OH)₂(LH)₂]Cl₂ and [Re(LH)₃](SO₄)₂·7H₂O have also been isolated. Biguanide complex of Re^{VII} in the protonated form has also been characterised. The compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental, magnetic, conductivity and ir spectral data.

Experimental

Potassium hexachlororhenate, K₂ReCl₆, was prepared¹ from potassium perrhenate. Biguanide and methyl biguanide were prepared from dicyandiamide following standard method². All the other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of complexes :

[ReO(OH)L₂] : Biguanidium acid sulphate (or its methyl derivative equivalent) (2.5 g, 0.0125 mol) made alkaline with NaOH was added to a saturated aqueous solution of potassium hexachlororhenate (1 g, 0.002 mol). The resulting violet solution was exposed to air for 8-10 h for oxidation, when a rose crystalline solid [ReO(OH)(L)₂] separated